

SCALEDem

ScaleDem Analytical Framework: Four Dimensions for Scaling Democratic Innovations/D1.1

WP1, T1.2

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Abstract

D1.1 is the first significant research output of the Horizon Europe ScaleDem project and represents an initial step toward inductively developing a theory of scaling democratic innovations. Building on literature in both the fields of social innovation and democratic innovation, this deliverable offers essential conceptual clarity by developing a multi-dimensional analytical framework that helps make sense of how democratic innovations can grow beyond isolated pilots to achieve broader and more lasting impact. It first unpacks four core scaling directions: embedding into formal institutions (Scaling High), expanding across people and places (Scaling Out), shaping civic culture and values (Scaling Deep), and enhancing process quality (Scaling In). It then identifies common barriers to scaling and organises enabling conditions across macro (institutional and political), meso (innovation-specific), and micro (actor-related) levels that may support overcoming these obstacles. Finally, it examines how these different scaling dimensions can interact, reinforce, or sometimes constrain each other through feedback loops.

Importantly, this framework does not seek to establish causal laws or offer a universal formula for success. Instead, it serves as an analytical scaffold to structure observations, clarify key concepts, and support more realistic, adaptable strategies for scaling democratic innovations in diverse contexts. By laying this foundation, D1.1 sets the stage for the next phases of the project, including developing a Theory of Change and conducting comparative empirical research, notably using QCA. It ultimately aims to assist researchers, practitioners, and policymakers in assessing scaling pathways and thinking more strategically about how democratic innovations can achieve wider and more durable impact.

Executive Summary

Why ScaleDem?

Across Europe and beyond, democracy is going through a difficult phase. Public trust is under pressure, political polarisation is rising, and many people feel that decision-making is distant or unresponsive. In response, governments, civil society, and international actors have increasingly turned to **democratic innovations**: practical ways of involving people more directly in shaping public decisions (for example, citizens' assemblies, participatory budgeting, digital participation tools, referenda, or reforms that improve electoral inclusion and fairness).

We know much more today about *what* democratic innovations are and *what they can achieve*. But a key challenge remains: **how do these innovations move beyond pilot projects and become sustainable parts of democratic life?** Many promising initiatives remain isolated experiments, while others travel, grow, and endure. ScaleDem addresses this “implementation gap” by focusing on a central question:

What helps democratic innovations scale — and why do some scale in some contexts, but not in others?

ScaleDem is a Horizon Europe project launched in December 2024. It builds tools and evidence that help practitioners, policymakers, and researchers understand the conditions under which democratic innovations expand, embed, and endure.

What this deliverable provides

This deliverable (D1.1) offers an **analytical framework** to map and compare scaling processes. It is not a “grand theory” that claims to predict outcomes everywhere. Instead, it provides a structured way to:

- describe *how* an innovation scales (and in which direction),
- identify common barriers and enabling conditions,
- and guide the empirical work of the project toward an evidence-based **Theory of Scaling**.

A four-dimensional view of scaling

Scaling is often understood as “getting bigger” or “reaching more people.” Our framework argues that scaling is **multi-dimensional**. A democratic innovation can grow in different ways — and may grow strongly in one direction while remaining limited in another.

We distinguish four complementary directions:

1) Scaling Out – reaching wider and broader publics

Scaling Out is about an innovation spreading horizontally: being replicated in new places, expanding participation, or travelling across organisations and policy areas. A participatory budgeting model that spreads from one city to many is an example of Scaling Out.

2) Scaling High – embedding in formal decision-making

Scaling High refers to innovations becoming integrated into formal structures and routines. This includes institutional endorsement, uptake of outputs (recommendations, votes, priorities), and long-term anchoring through resources and procedures. For example, when an innovation becomes mandated by rules, regulations, or stable organisational commitments, it is scaling high.

3) Scaling Deep – shaping democratic culture and dispositions

Scaling Deep captures changes “inside people and communities”: trust, democratic norms, civic identity, learning, and lasting engagement. An innovation scales deep when participation strengthens democratic attachment and helps people see themselves as capable democratic actors.

4) Scaling In – improving the quality and integrity of the process

Scaling In focuses on the quality of what happens “inside” the innovation: inclusiveness, integrity, effectiveness, and learning over time. It asks whether an innovation can grow **without losing quality**, and whether it can continuously improve its own design through feedback and adaptation.

Why context matters

Scaling is rarely straightforward. Every innovation faces trade-offs and constraints — and these vary across countries, regions, and innovation families. What works in one setting may require adaptation in another. For example, a legal framework that enables participation in one country may block it elsewhere; resource capacity, political incentives, and civic norms also differ widely.

For this reason, ScaleDem treats scaling as **context-sensitive and configurational**: outcomes are expected to result from **combinations** of enabling conditions and constraints, rather than single “magic” factors.

Barriers and enabling conditions: what typically blocks or supports scaling?

This deliverable maps five broad families of barriers that frequently shape whether scaling occurs:

- **Institutional barriers:** administrative inertia, rigid procedures, lack of capacity
- **Political resistance:** reluctance of elites to share power, weak uptake of citizen input
- **Cultural barriers:** low civic trust, polarisation, weak traditions of participation
- **Resource constraints:** insufficient funding, limited expertise, overstretched staff
- **Design limitations:** formats that are not inclusive, not transferable, or hard to sustain

At the same time, scaling can be supported by enabling conditions such as:

- **Institutional support:** stable funding, mandates, administrative embedding

- **Political will and leadership:** champions who protect and promote the innovation
- **Civic readiness:** norms and networks that support participation and deliberation
- **High-quality and adaptable design:** formats that can be transferred without “cloning”
- **Learning capacity:** evaluation and feedback mechanisms that improve quality over time

A core practical insight is that scaling rarely means copying a model unchanged. More often, it involves **adapting without reinventing**: reusing what works, while adjusting design to local institutional and cultural conditions.

How the framework will be tested: Knowledge Map + comparative analysis

D1.1 is a conceptual framework, but it is designed for empirical testing. ScaleDem’s next steps build a bridge from framework to evidence.

A key tool here is the **ScaleDem Knowledge Map**: a structured and regularly updated database that maps research-and-innovation-driven democratic innovations and classifies them by innovation family and scaling features. It supports comparison, trend detection, and systematic case selection.

To analyse patterns across cases, ScaleDem uses **Qualitative Comparative Analysis (QCA)** as a comparative backbone. QCA is designed to identify recurring **configurations** (combinations) of conditions associated with different scaling outcomes. This aligns with the framework’s central assumption: scaling trajectories are not driven by one factor alone, but by interacting conditions that may differ across contexts.

QCA will be complemented by **dimension-specific methods** (for deeper interpretation and causal insight), including qualitative and mixed-method approaches such as document analysis, surveys, Delphi exercises, interviews, focus groups, and process tracing. Together, these methods help connect comparative patterns (“what tends to scale under what conditions?”) to mechanism-sensitive explanations (“how and why did scaling unfold in a given case?”).

What comes next: toward a Theory of Scaling

This analytical framework is a first step in a larger pipeline. ScaleDem’s next deliverables will progressively build an empirically grounded **Theory of Scaling** that explains:

- why some innovations scale in one dimension but not others,
- how scaling dimensions reinforce one another (or create tensions),
- which enabling conditions matter most in which contexts,
- and what practical strategies help innovations travel, embed, and endure.

The ambition is to move from mapping and comparison to actionable knowledge: a clearer understanding of **what scales, under which conditions, and why** — and how actors can use that knowledge to design more sustainable democratic innovations.

Dimensionality of Scaling: Conceptual Gaps and Emerging Questions

As democratic innovations have proliferated in Europe and beyond, attention has shifted from experimenting with new formats toward understanding how these practices do not remain confined to isolated pilot projects but instead can achieve broader and more lasting impact at the core of the democratic fabric. In this context, the challenge of scaling becomes more and more prominent. While the difficulty of enlarging the demos and direct democratic practices to larger and larger polities was thought to be the main challenge to democracy-beyond-the-polis by the philosophers of Antiquity, the question of democratic “scale” was later conceptualized by Robert Dahl (1989) primarily in terms of the size and level of democratic governance. Dahl’s notion of scale concerns how democracy can function in larger and more complex political units, rather than the processes through which democratic practices spread, take root, or deepen over time. In contrast, the concept of scaling as used in this project refers to these dynamic processes of diffusion, institutional embedding, cultural transformation, and qualitative consolidation). Other fields, however, have long developed nuanced frameworks that help unpack its multiple dimensions.

In social innovation studies, Moore et al. (2015) distinguish between “scaling out”, which entails replicating or spreading innovations to reach wider populations or geographies; “scaling up”, which involves embedding innovations into broader institutional or policy systems to achieve systemic change; and “scaling deep”, which seeks to transform cultural values and relationships to sustain long-term impacts. Westley et al. (2014) similarly highlight that scaling can take varied configurations, beyond simple replication, requiring strategic engagement with complex systems to secure enduring influence. In the domain of sustainability transitions, Augenstein et al. (2020) discuss the inherent dilemmas in moving sustainable alternatives from protected niches to the mainstream, cautioning that “upscaling” often involves compromises between transformative aims and integration into dominant regimes. Building on this tradition, Lam et al. (2020) offer an integrative synthesis by reviewing six prominent amplification frameworks and proposing a typology of eight processes — stabilising, speeding up, growing, replicating, transferring, spreading, scaling up, and scaling deep — grouped into three broader categories of *amplifying within*, *amplifying out*, and *amplifying beyond*. Their contribution underscores that scaling is better understood as a bundle of distinct but interacting processes than as a single trajectory. Bauwens et al. (2022) extend this reasoning by examining how community enterprises navigate institutional complexity when upscaling, emphasizing that expansion frequently necessitates shifts in governance structures and legitimacy to reach broader user groups. From a wider systems-change perspective, Kania, Kramer and Senge (2018) argue that durable impact depends on shifting six interconnected conditions — policies, practices, resource flows, relationships, power dynamics, and mental models — operating across explicit, semi-explicit, and transformative levels. Collectively, this body of work underscores that scaling is neither linear nor purely quantitative: it spans institutional embedding, geographic diffusion, and cultural shifts. By contrast, the concept of scaling in the field of democratic innovations has so far received only fragmented attention. Scholars have long explored how democratic innovations (DIs) can grow and achieve *broader significance*, emphasizing various dimensions such as integrating participatory mechanisms for wider coverage and

more robust engagement (Spada & Allegretti, 2017), fostering diffusion and uptake across levels of government (Smith, 2019), enhancing the geographical expansion, sustainability, and reach of participatory formats (Pradeau, 2021), or amplify participants' attitudes, behaviours, and capabilities (Theuwis et al., 2025). In this respect, it is also important to clarify that scaling is not synonymous with *impact*, for which a large body of literature already exists (Jacquet, et al., 2023). Niemeyer (2014) provides one of the earliest systematic discussions on scaling by exploring how deliberative mini publics might scale up to influence mass publics within a deliberative system. Yet his focus remains primarily on informational flows and institutional linkages of deliberative mini publics, rather than offering a comprehensive multi-dimensional framework for scaling participatory processes more broadly. A more structurally ambitious early attempt was made by Vergne (2013), who proposed a framework distinguishing two overarching dimensions of scaling — **physical** (territory, number of participants, time) and **substantial** (impact on decision-making, deliberative quality, and scope or reach of the process) — complemented by an **internal** dimension of organisational complexity. Drawing on seven empirical cases, he argued that while each sub-dimension can in principle be scaled independently, multidimensional scaling rapidly generates trade-offs: deliberative quality, in particular, tends to deteriorate beyond certain thresholds of participant numbers or compressed timeframes, while territorial expansion sits uneasily with extended participatory timeframes. From this, Vergne proposed a *quantum* model of scaling — in which threshold effects and dimension-specific dynamics displace the notion of smooth, unidimensional expansion — and emphasised the importance of reading affinities and negative correlations between dimensions rather than pursuing all at once. More recently, Arantzazulab (2023) has stressed the need for designing democratic experiments that can inspire replication and institutional adoption, but without elaborating scaling as a structured concept. A broad literature also addresses the question of scaling through digital tools. A first wave concentrated around the concept of “civic tech” and digital democracy, while an emerging literature is now examining scaling largely in the context of artificial intelligence as a means to expand or accelerate citizen deliberation (McKinney, 2024, 2025; McKinney and Chwalisz, 2025). However, these discussions often remain focused on the technological leverage for scaling, leaving broader questions around embeddedness or culture largely unaddressed.

As such, there is still no consolidated framework to guide how democratic innovations can systematically scale. This deliverable addresses this gap by proposing a multi-dimensional analytical framework to better capture the complexity of scaling DIs. Rather than assuming a single path or predictable outcome, we understand scaling as a dynamic, context-dependent process, shaped by institutional arrangements, cultural and political support, the design of innovations themselves, and the strategies of diverse actors who drive (or hinder) change. Building on insights from both previous research and practitioner experience, our aim is to offer a structured yet flexible lens through which to examine how scaling unfolds along four core scaling dimensions:

- **Scaling High:** Embedding the innovation into formal institutions—gaining traction in policymaking, laws and regulations, or administrative procedures.
- **Scaling Out:** Reaching more people and places by replicating the innovation across different settings and contexts or increasing the number of participants involved.
- **Scaling Deep:** Producing durable change in how people feel, think, relate, and act - thereby turning democratic innovations into ‘habits of the heart’.

- **Scaling In:** Strengthening the quality of the innovation by ensuring that it is ever more fair, inclusive, and deliberative.

These dimensions are deliberately framed using spatial signifiers to convey the direction and process of change inherent in scaling. Scaling describes how a democratic innovation evolves, expands, or embeds itself more deeply within a system, moving from one state to another. This is distinct from impact, which refers to the outcomes or results of an intervention at a specific point in time. While successful scaling can certainly enhance or multiply impact, the two are conceptually different: put simply, impact is static, scaling is moving. This raises important questions about the nature of scaling itself. Is it a process that unfolds autonomously, as if democratic innovations evolve like independent entities? Or is it a socially and politically driven process, actively constructed and carried forward by different actors who may vary depending on the dimension? How do these dimensions interact and influence one another? Exploring these questions is crucial for understanding scaling as more than an organic trajectory, but as a complex, actor-driven evolution shaped by varied contexts.

This working paper is intentionally positioned as a starting point. It does not present a comprehensive theory of scaling, nor does it seek to define concrete indicators or prescribe specific research designs. Instead, it offers an analytical anchor to clarify key concepts, outline initial operational definitions, and establish relevant levels of analysis. The goal is both analytical and practical: to provide a foundation that can help researchers, practitioners, and policymakers assess how democratic innovations scale, identify barriers and enabling factors, and think more strategically about where and how scaling might occur. Ultimately, this paper aims to stimulate reflection and dialogue within the broader community, inviting critical engagement that will inform and refine subsequent phases of the ScaleDem project.

The document proceeds as follows. Section 1 introduces the four scaling dimensions and outlines their definitions and potential indicators, providing an overview of scaling as a multidimensional process. Section 2 examines how scaling may occur — or fail to occur — by mapping key barriers and enabling factors across institutional, political, cultural, resource-based, and design-related layers. Section 3 explores the potential interactions between scaling dimensions and introduces the concept of scaling profiles, highlighting how different configurations may emerge across contexts. Section 4 presents the methodological framework and research design. The document concludes by outlining the next analytical steps and the development of a Theory of Change.

1. Unpacking Scaling Outcomes: Definitions and Potential Indicators

This section unpacks the four scaling dimensions (Scaling High, Out, Deep, and In) and proposes a structured set of potential indicators for each. The objective is to establish a common analytical architecture for examining what it means for democratic innovations to scale.

Democratic innovations do not constitute a single institutional model. The literature identifies several families of mechanisms through which democratic governance can be reconfigured. These include deliberative forums that bring together diverse or randomly selected citizens for structured and informed dialogue (e.g., Geissel & Gerghina, 2016); direct democratic instruments that grant citizens binding decision-making power through referenda and initiatives (e.g., Michels and de Graaf, 2010; Magni-Berton, 2025); participatory and co-production mechanisms that involve citizens more broadly in public decision-making processes (Goulart & Falanga, 2022); digital and AI-enabled participation tools that mediate civic engagement through technological platforms (e.g., Mikhaylovskaya & Rouméas, 2024); administrative innovations that embed citizen participation within the structures and routines of public administration, including permanent oversight or co-management arrangements (Røiseland & Vabo, 2020); and electoral innovations aimed at reforming voting systems and representative institutions (e.g., Lago & Martinez i Coma, 2023).

These families differ in institutional design, normative orientation, and mechanisms of citizen involvement. The project explicitly accounts for this variation and, as it will be explained in Section 2, is bound to examine how scaling trajectories may differ across these families. However, the present section privileges the scaling perspective: it develops a cross-cutting analytical framework that applies across innovation families, rather than elaborating family-specific typologies at this stage. Systematic analysis of how scaling varies across innovation families and contexts will be undertaken in subsequent phases of the project through the Knowledge Map — a structured and progressively expanding database of cases — and through empirical analyses (see Section 4).

The indicators proposed below are illustrative and non-exhaustive. They are intended to guide future operationalisation into concrete empirical measures, a step that lies beyond the scope of the present document.

1.1 Scaling High: institutional embedding and political uptake

Scaling High refers to the integration of democratic innovations into the formal structures, processes, and decision-making frameworks of institutions. While previous studies used this expression to indicate DIs movement across territorial levels of governance (for example, from local to national) (Pogrebinschi & Ryan, 2018), we think it provides an effective spatial metaphor capturing more broadly DIs institutional ascent — that is, when innovations become recognised, embedded, or mandated within any type of formal organisation at any level. This broader scope reflects a growing body of work demonstrating that democratic and participatory practices can take root not only in

public administrations but also within firms and non-state organisations (Ferrerias, 2017; Pateman, 1970; Fung & Wright, 2003). What distinguishes Scaling High from Scaling Out (see below) — which addresses the *spread* of DIs across different types of actors and institutional settings — is its focus on the *depth* of embedding within a given organisation: the degree to which an innovation moves from peripheral or experimental use to a recognised, resourced, and routinised feature of how that organisation operates. While this dimension of scaling is most extensively documented in public sector contexts, and the present framework draws primarily on that literature, the analytical structure proposed here is intended to apply across institutional types. The mechanisms described below therefore refer to generic processes of institutional embedding, rather than to sector-specific governance arrangements.

There are three broad overlapping dimensions of integration. The first dimension is **leadership and governance buy-in**. This is a necessary element of Scaling High and refers to the extent to which democratic innovations secure endorsement at the leadership or governance level of an organisation and achieve relevance within its decision-making processes. It includes the presence of internal champions — whether elected officials, executives, board members, or senior administrators — as well as one-off or ad hoc mandates that authorise the use of a democratic innovation within a given organisational context. It also includes decision uptake, that is, the extent to which the outputs of democratic innovations — such as votes, recommendations, priorities, or citizen proposals — are formally considered, adopted, or implemented in the organisation's decision-making processes. Leadership and governance buy-in therefore captures situations in which democratic innovations have substantive influence, even where the process itself is not yet durably embedded in formal structures. While this dimension is most extensively documented in public and political settings, where it manifests as political will and policy relevance, the underlying dynamic — that an innovation requires authorisation and recognition from those who hold decision-making power — applies equally to firms and civil society organisations.

The second dimension is **operational integration**. This concerns the extent to which democratic innovations are taken up within the operational and managerial structures of an organisation and used in ways that strengthen its effectiveness, coordination, and internal capacity. In many cases, democratic innovations are first enacted through pre-existing organisational frameworks rather than through entirely new structures. Their repeated or experimental use may then generate adaptive and iterative learning, with designs progressively adjusted to purpose and context. Over time, this can contribute to stronger organisational capacity by increasing awareness, developing internal knowledge and expertise, and reducing reliance on external facilitators or consultants. Operational integration may also involve formalised follow-up mechanisms — such as requirements for monitoring, reporting, or implementation — which help organisations connect participatory outputs to their internal routines and responsibilities.

The third dimension is **structural and formal anchoring**. This refers to the extent to which democratic innovations become consolidated within the longer-term formal architecture of an organisation rather than remaining isolated or one-off experiments. It includes formal anchoring, such as stable and sustained financial commitments, recurring or multi-year budget allocations, and recognition in binding instruments — whether legal or regulatory frameworks in the case of public authorities, or

founding documents, bylaws, or governance frameworks in the case of companies and civil society organisations. It also includes procedural integration, namely the incorporation of democratic innovations into formal procedures, decision-making cycles, or organisational routines. In this sense, structural anchoring signals that democratic innovations are no longer peripheral or exceptional but are connected to the ordinary machinery of the organisation through stable resources, formal recognition, and routinised links to decision-making processes. It is worth noting that the empirical evidence underpinning this sub-dimension is drawn primarily from public sector and civil society contexts, where the pathways to official embedding are best documented; equivalent anchoring mechanisms in the private sector remain an underexplored area that this framework invites future research to address.

We propose below a summary table outlining the internal dimensions and sub-components of the Scaling High concept. As with the other scaling dimensions presented in this framework, this conceptual and analytical mapping is intended to facilitate the future operationalization of these concepts into concrete indicators for empirical research.

Table 1. Scaling High: Sub-Dimensions and Operational Structure

Sub-dimension	Indicator family	Illustrative indicators
<i>Leadership & governance buy-in</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Governing-body endorsement</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Internal champions or mandate-holders at leadership or governance level; one-off or standing organisational mandate for DI</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Decision uptake</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Formal consideration, adoption, or implementation of DI outputs in decision-making processes</i>
<i>Operational Integration</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Mandated follow-up mechanisms</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Existence of formally required monitoring, reporting, or implementation provisions</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Adaptive/iterative DI design</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Experimental, iterative use of DIs, responsive to purpose and context</i> • <i>Use of pre-existing frameworks to enact DI</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Increased organisational capacity</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Increased awareness and knowledge within the organisation; reduced reliance on external facilitators or consultants</i>

<i>Structural and Formal Anchoring</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Formal/institutional anchoring</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Evidence of stable and sustained financial commitment; multi-year or recurring budget allocation; formal recognition in binding legal, regulatory, or constitutional instruments</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Formal integration</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Formal recognition in binding legal, regulatory, or constitutional instruments</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Procedural integration</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Incorporation into formal procedures, decision-making cycles, or organisational routines</i>

1.2 Scaling Out: Expanding Democratic Innovations Across People and Places

Scaling Out is perhaps the most easily grasped dimension of scaling. It refers to how democratic innovations expand in three directions, ‘horizontally’ (expanding across new places, institutions and kind of institutions, and/or policy domains), ‘vertically’ (across level of governance) and ‘transversally’ (extending the scope of participants towards including more and new participants).

Importantly, Scaling Out is not simply about replication as “copy–paste.” Research on policy transfer, diffusion, and circulation shows that innovations rarely travel unchanged: they are translated, adapted, and reassembled as they encounter different institutional traditions, administrative routines, and cultural meaning systems (de Oliveira, 2021; Pradeau, 2021; Romano, 2021). This implies that scaling out often involves adapting without reinventing: preserving core features while adjusting design and implementation to new contexts.

The first aspect of Scaling Out centres around the kind of institutions activating DI and for what. An innovation might begin in one city or municipality, and later be adapted or adopted in other towns, regions, or countries. This **horizontal scaling** demonstrates that an idea or method can travel beyond its original home, responding to the needs of different communities and adapting to different contexts. Replication also takes the form of thematic or sectoral spread: for instance, a DI used in environmental policy might later be applied in education or public health. Finally, horizontal scaling can concern the spread to other types of institutions: from public authorities to companies / civil society organizations or, vice versa, from management techniques within companies to public authorities.

The second direction is **vertical**, across levels of governance. An innovation implemented at the local level may later be adopted on the regional or national scale. DIs deployed at global and/or international level may inspire or set the scene for national/regional/ local replications.

The third direction of scaling out is **transversal** and refers to an increasing number of citizens directly involved in a single democratic innovation. When these innovations include more participants over time or reach a higher percentage of eligible or affected populations, they are expanding their footprint in a meaningful way. However, numbers alone do not tell the full story. Who participates matters just as much. For this reason, attention to the *diversity* of participation is also key: are young people involved? Are people with lower incomes, minority backgrounds, or different education levels present? Are gender backgrounds equally given the opportunity to participate in DIs? And beyond: are non-humans or future generations included as well? All these questions help assess whether the innovation is reaching not only more people, but also a more diverse cross-section of society.

Table 2. Scaling Out: Sub-Dimensions and Operational Structure

Sub-dimension	Indicator family	Illustrative indicators
Horizontal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Institutional replication</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Implementation by the same or another institution of a similar type of the DI beyond the original site, whether within the same regional context or across different regional or national settings</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Institutional-type diversification</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Uptake by different types of actors (e.g., public authorities, hybrid and/or private bodies, civic-led organisation)</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Policy-domain diffusion</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Implementation across multiple policy issue areas</i>
Vertical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Governance-level uptake</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Adoption and/or implementation across local, regional, national, and/or supranational levels of governance</i>
Transversal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Participant expansion</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Increase in total number of participants across replications</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Participant diversification</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Inclusion of new and/or underrepresented socio-demographic groups and or types of demos (more-than-human, future generations)</i>

1.3 Scaling Deep: Generating emotional, cognitive, and behavioural change

Scaling Deep refers to the extent to which a democratic innovation produces durable, inward-facing change — transforming how people feel, think and value, identify and behave democratically, both individually and collectively. Where Scaling Out tracks the spread of innovations across places and people, Scaling High their embedding in formal structures, and Scaling In the improvement of their internal processes, Scaling Deep asks a different question: does participation leave a lasting mark on those who experience it, and through them, on the broader democratic culture in which they live? In the ScaleDem framework, this dimension captures transformations in emotions, meanings, norms, identities, capacities, and behavioural dispositions — the psychologically accumulated sediment of democratic life rather than its institutional or procedural architecture.

The contemporary interdisciplinary anchors of the ideas behind this dimension draw on a long tradition in classic democratic theory. Alexis de Tocqueville's concept of *mœurs* — the moral and intellectual habits that give life to democratic institutions, which he on occasion called “habits of the heart” (*Democracy in America*, 1835/1840) — captures the idea that democracy depends not only on laws and procedures, but on the dispositions, values, and everyday civic practices that citizens carry with them and reproduce over time. John Dewey extended this insight by arguing that democracy was not primarily a form of government but “a mode of associated living, of conjoint communicated experience” (*Democracy and Education*, 1916) where participation in shared deliberation and collective problem-solving transformed the habits, dispositions, and moral outlooks of those who engage in it, making democratic practice itself the school of democratic character. Robert N. Bellah et al. (1985) argued that commitment to community and democratic participation must be understood as cultivated habits embedded in social relationships and cultural meanings, rather than merely as rational choices. Carole Pateman's (1970) foundational claim that participation itself has an educative function — that engaging in democratic processes develops the very capacities required for further democratic engagement — provides the theoretical mechanism linking exposure to democratic innovations to the deeper transformations this dimension seeks to capture.

More recently, the political-cultural, psychological and sociological research on democratic innovations has further elaborated these claims. Luc Theuwis et al. (2025), in a meta-analysis spanning four decades of evidence, find that participation in democratic innovations produces measurable effects on participants' attitudes, behaviours, and capabilities — including increased political knowledge, efficacy, and willingness to engage — though the durability and diffusion of these effects beyond direct participants remains an open empirical question that Scaling Deep specifically aims to address. Sergiu Gherghina and Birgit Geissel (2017) similarly show that democratic preferences and participation are mutually reinforcing over time, suggesting participation can deepen democratic orientations rather than simply reflect pre-existing ones. Changes induced by Scaling Deep processes can be experienced or observed by people through the lenses of five interrelated layers: the emotional, cognitive, normative, identity and behavioural:

The **emotional** layer captures change regarding democratic trust and satisfaction — the affective orientation of individuals toward democratic processes, institutions, and fellow citizens. Deepening along this dimension involves growing trust, hope, and a sense of belonging, alongside declining fear or cynicism about political engagement.

The **cognitive** sub-dimension addresses changes in understanding or sense-making, in perspective-taking and political knowledge — that is whether democratic innovations induce citizens to reason more carefully, engage with complexity and the perspectives of others.

The **normative** sub-dimension concerns shifts in the values and principles citizens bring to democratic life — not merely regarding what they feel or know about politics, but what they think democracy is *for* and how they believe they and others ought to engage within it. Normative change of this kind is arguably a deeper and more consequential impact of scaling deep, since values and principles are more stable orientational frames through which individuals interpret political experiences, evaluate institutions, and decide how to act. A democratic innovation that leaves participants with a richer, more exacting, or more genuinely held set of democratic values does something that no institutional

reform alone can accomplish: it changes the normative fabric from which democratic behaviour is woven. The substance of normative change varies across families of democratic innovations, and this variation must be taken seriously analytically. In deliberative settings, the relevant normative shift concerns what might be called *deliberative values* — commitment to reason-giving, listening, reciprocity, tolerance of disagreement, and the acceptance of outcomes reached through fair and open discussion (Gutmann & Thompson, 1997; Bächtiger et al., 2018). In direct democratic settings, the core normative referents are popular sovereignty, civic duty, and the principle of collective self-determination — the belief that citizens are and ought to be the authors of the rules under which they live (Barber, 1984; Altman, 2011). In electoral innovations, the relevant shift is toward a stronger commitment to political equality, fair representation, and the accountability of those who hold power to those over whom it is exercised (Dahl, 1989; Norris, 2004).

The fourth is the **symbolic and identity** sub-dimension, which captures shifts in how individuals understand themselves as democratic actors: changes in political efficacy, in the sense of being counted and having a voice, and in self-identification as an active member of a democratic community. Central to this sub-dimension is the experience of belonging — the felt sense of being part of a community of shared purpose that extends beyond the individual self. This is not merely a normative aspiration: psychological research has established belonging as a fundamental human motivation, as basic and pervasive as other primary needs, with direct consequences for emotional patterns, cognitive processes, and wellbeing (Leary & Baumeister, 1995). Neuroscientific evidence reinforces this: social participation in groups has measurable structural and functional correlates in the human brain — particularly in the default mode and limbic networks — suggesting that the experience of group membership and civic belonging operates at a deep psychobiological level, not only at the level of consciously held attitudes or identities (Seidel et al., 2023). Democratic innovations that generate genuine belonging among participants may therefore activate change processes that are more durable and embodied than those captured by conventional attitudinal measures alone.

The fifth and final one is the **behavioural** sub-dimension, which addresses whether deepened democratic dispositions translate into sustained civic action — continued participation, civic initiative, and democratic engagement beyond the original innovative initiative.

Table 3. Scaling Deep: Sub-Dimensions and Operational Structure

Sub-Dimension	Indicator family	Illustrative indicators
<i>Emotional</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Democratic trust and satisfaction</i> 	<i>Trust, hope, belonging, reduced fear or cynicism</i>
<i>Normative</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Democratic values and deliberative principles</i> 	<i>Commitment to fairness, listening, pluralism, reason-giving</i>
<i>Cognitive</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Political understanding and perspective taking</i> 	<i>Increased political knowledge, nuanced views, appreciation of complexity</i>

<i>Symbolic /Identity</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Democratic agency and identification</i> 	<i>Political efficacy, feeling heard, self-identification as democratic actor</i>
<i>Behavioural</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Sustained civic habits and engagement</i> 	<i>Continued participation, civic monitoring, initiative-taking, durable engagement beyond initial innovation</i>

The sub-dimensions identified here are conceptualised as cross-cutting and applicable across innovation families. However, the ways in which these transformations occur may vary across deliberative, direct, participatory, digital, administrative, and electoral innovations. This variation will be carefully examined in subsequent phases of the project.

1.4. Scaling In: enhancing process quality

Scaling In refers to the capacity of a democratic innovation to preserve and continually improve the quality of its own processes (a better referendum; a better digital platform, etc). Where Scaling Out asks how far an innovation reaches, Scaling High how it embeds in formal structures, and Scaling Deep what lasting traces it leaves in people and cultures, Scaling In asks: how does the process become better over time? It is not only concerned with who is reached or where the innovation travels, but with the integrity of what happens inside the participatory space — and with whether that quality can be sustained, deepened, and built upon across successive cycles. This dimension resonates with widely recognised quality standards and ethical benchmarks for public participation processes, such as those set out in Dienel et al. (2014), the OECD Guidelines for Citizen Participation Processes (OECD, 2022), and with the growing literature on the governance and integrity of deliberative mini-publics (Curato & Parry, 2024; Parry & Curato, 2025). It also carries a specific relationship to Scaling Out: as processes expand in participant numbers and geographic reach, the risk of quality erosion grows, making Scaling In particularly demanding and necessary as other dimensions advance.

The first sub-dimension is **inclusiveness**. This concerns whether different kinds of people are concretely ensured equal access, visibility, speaking turns, and meaningful participation throughout the process — not only at the point of recruitment, but across the full participatory cycle. It is important to distinguish between two analytically separate but mutually reinforcing concerns. The first is *structural inclusion*: whether the design of the process removes barriers to participation — barriers of geography, language, literacy, economic cost, caring responsibilities, or physical accessibility — such that different people can enter the DI space in the first place. The second is *interactional inclusion*: whether, once inside the process, participants are able to contribute on genuinely equal terms.

The second sub-dimension is **integrity**. This refers to the extent to which a democratic innovation operates through transparent, accountable, and genuinely fair practices — and that it continues to do so as it grows and evolves. Process integrity can be understood across three overlapping dimensions that apply, with different empirical content, across all families of democratic innovations:

1. The first is the **procedural dimension**: whether the rules governing the process are clear, consistently applied, and publicly accessible. In deliberative settings, this means clarity of facilitation rules, structured agendas, and explicit standards for how arguments are presented and responded to. In direct democratic processes, it means transparency and neutrality of ballot design and question framing, and clarity about what the vote can and cannot decide. In electoral innovations, it means the transparency of counting procedures, candidate eligibility criteria, and the rules governing access to electoral infrastructure. In administrative and co-production innovations, it means clear documentation of how citizen inputs are processed and what weight they are given in decisions.
2. The second is the **relational dimension**: whether participants, voters, or citizens are treated with equal respect and given genuine — rather than merely formal — hearing. In deliberative settings, this requires that opposing views are heard without personal attack or group entrenchment, and that no single voice or coalition dominates the exchange. In direct democracy, it requires that all voters have access to balanced information and that disinformation or manipulation of campaign conditions is actively countered. In electoral processes, it requires equal treatment of candidates, fair access to media and public platforms, and equal valuation of votes. In co-production, it requires that citizen contributions are genuinely considered rather than selectively incorporated to ratify decisions already made — the difference between substantive and tokenistic participation.
3. The third is the **governance dimension**: whether the process has independent oversight capable of holding it accountable to its own stated standards. High-quality processes do not arise spontaneously and cannot be self-certifying — they depend on design, management, and accountability structures that sit at least partly outside the immediate interests of those who commission or benefit from them. A process whose integrity is structurally compromised — by conflicts of interest in its design, selective reporting of outputs, absence of independent audit, or regulatory capture of oversight bodies — cannot achieve genuine Scaling In regardless of how technically well-run its individual sessions or ballots are.

It is worth noting that across all three dimensions, the risk of integrity failure grows as democratic innovations scale along other dimensions. Expanding participation (Scaling Out) increases the complexity of managing fair facilitation and balanced information access. Institutional embedding (Scaling High) can introduce bureaucratic incentives that prioritise efficiency or political acceptability over procedural rigour. Scaling In therefore functions as a quality check on the other dimensions — ensuring that what spreads and embeds is genuinely worth having.

The third sub-dimension is **effectiveness**. Democratic processes must not only feel fair — they must also function well. This means adhering to clear agendas, maintaining coherence over time, and producing tangible outputs — recommendations, decisions, priorities — that are recognisably connected to the deliberation that generated them. Process-output coherence is central here:

participants must be able to see how their contributions shaped what emerged, and commissioning institutions must have clear and enforceable obligations to respond to what the process produced (Pogrebinschi & Ryan, 2018). A process that breaks down, loses internal direction, or produces outputs that are systematically ignored or distorted risks not only wasting participants' time but actively producing disillusionment — undermining the very civic dispositions that Scaling Deep seeks to cultivate. Effectiveness therefore has an accountability dimension that connects Scaling In to the other dimensions: a process whose outputs are taken seriously is more likely to deepen civic engagement (Scaling Deep) and more likely to achieve institutional embedding (Scaling High). Scaling In requires that processes progressively improve their capacity to produce outputs that are both substantively credible and consequentially relevant — that is, outputs which participants recognise as their own and which decision-makers cannot easily set aside.

The fourth sub-dimension is **learning and feedback capacity**. Innovations that scale well internally are those that build systematic mechanisms for reflecting on their own performance and improving over successive iterations (Campos et al., 2024). This capacity is not merely desirable — without it, even well-designed processes will stagnate, reproduce their failures, and gradually diverge from the quality standards they initially claimed.

Table 4. Scaling In: Sub-Dimensions and Operational Structure

Sub-Dimension	Indicator family	Illustrative indicators
Inclusiveness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Structural access 	Design features that broaden and stabilise access across geographic, linguistic, socio-economic, and digital differences
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interactional balance 	Facilitation or design mechanisms ensuring diverse voices are heard; safeguards against domination; balanced participation across stakeholder groups
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sustained inclusion 	Monitoring and correction of participation imbalances across the full process cycle
Integrity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Procedural clarity 	Clear and transparent rules, publicly accessible criteria, consistent application of procedures
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Relational fairness 	Equal respect and genuine hearing; avoidance of tokenistic engagement; balanced information provision
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Independent oversight 	Monitoring or audit mechanisms capable of assessing procedural integrity

<i>Effectiveness</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Process-output coherence</i> 	<i>Clear linkage between participant input and outputs; transparent explanation of how contributions shaped decisions</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Tangible impact capacity</i> 	<i>Production of actionable outputs; visible implementation; formal response obligations</i>
<i>Continuity and Robustness</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Organisational resilience</i> 	<i>Capacity to sustain or repeat the innovation over time</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Contextual robustness</i> 	<i>Ability to withstand political, financial, or organisational changes without erosion of core quality standards</i>
<i>Learning and Feedback Capacity</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Reflexive evaluation</i> 	<i>Regular monitoring and structured assessment of process quality against explicit criteria</i>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Adaptive capacity</i> 	<i>Evidence of design adjustments or improvements across cycles; incorporation of evaluation findings into subsequent iterations</i>

2. Scaling Settings: Overcoming Scaling Barriers

Scaling democratic innovations, in any dimension, encounters obstacles similar to those observed in other areas of social and policy innovation (e.g., van Lunenburg et al., 2020; van Hout et al., 2024). These constraints vary across contexts but can be analytically grouped into five broad categories: institutional, political, cultural, resource-based, and design-related. The first two operate primarily at the macro level, shaping the broader political and institutional environment in which innovations unfold. The next two are often linked to micro-level characteristics of the actors initiating or implementing the innovation. Finally, design-related factors concern the meso level — the internal architecture, procedural rules, and underlying model of the innovation itself (e.g., deliberative, digital/AI-based, participatory, administrative, direct democratic, or electoral).

Importantly, barriers and enabling conditions rarely operate in isolation. Their relative weight and interaction vary across innovation families, regional settings and institutional environments. What constitutes an institutional constraint in one context may function as a facilitator in another, depending on political opportunity structures, administrative traditions, resource configurations, and prevailing participatory norms. As research on policy transfer and circulation demonstrates, innovations do not travel unchanged across contexts; they are translated, adapted, and reassembled through interaction with institutional traditions and cultural meaning systems (De Oliveira, 2021; Pradeau, 2021; Romano, 2021). Scaling outcomes therefore emerge from context-specific configurations of constraints and enabling factors. As shown in Section 4, our methodological design explicitly accounts for this configurational and context-sensitive character of scaling dynamics, enabling us to identify what scales, under which conditions, and why.

2.1 Listing Most Common Scaling Barriers

The list below provides a general overview of the main barriers to scaling democratic innovations. While it does not aim to be exhaustive in capturing every specific case, it is intended to map the broad categories under which most common obstacles to scaling democratic innovations can be grouped.

Starting from the macro level, one major barrier is structural in nature. In many places, public administrations often operate under incentive structures that prioritize control, efficiency, and risk-aversion over responsiveness or innovation. This can lead to a lack of motivation to create or engage with participatory mechanisms, especially when such mechanisms are not legally mandated or politically incentivized (Pogrebinschi & Ryan, 2018; Ruijter & Meijer, 2020). Even where there is openness to experimentation, bureaucratic systems frequently lack the capacity, coordination, or flexibility to adapt. Institutional inertia, rigid procedures, and a limited culture of public engagement continue to prevent democratic innovations from being more systematically embedded into governance (Meier et al., 2019; Corbett, 2018).

A second set of ‘macro’ challenges is socio-political. Political elites may see democratic innovations as a threat to their authority or control over decision-making. They may resist these processes outright or subtly undermine them by selectively embracing results that fit their agenda while ignoring others (Sønderskov, 2020; Junius et al., 2020). In other cases, elites may simply be indifferent, or sceptical

of citizens' ability to contribute meaningfully, especially in complex or technical domains (Barry & Bannister, 2014). These dynamics can create a political environment where citizen participation is tolerated but not taken seriously.

At the individual level, barriers can be cultural and cognitive. People may lack confidence in their own ability to engage or have limited civic knowledge and experience with deliberative norms (Gastil & Richards, 2013). More broadly, this also includes limited understanding of political facts, or low ideological and political sophistication (Kinder and Kalmoe, 2017), which can inhibit meaningful engagement and deliberation. These factors can lead to low participation, weak trust in the process, or an inability to scale innovations across different settings (Christensen et al., 2016; Landwehr & Faas, 2016).

Resource constraints can represent another individual-level barrier, especially for initiatives run at the local level or by civil society actors. Democratic innovations require time, money, skills (facilitation, project management, campaigning, programming, communication, etc), and networks of support. When funding is unstable, staff are overstretched, or access to technology or expertise is limited, it becomes difficult to sustain or replicate innovations (Barry & Bannister, 2014; Schradie, 2018; Janssen et al., 2012). These challenges are particularly acute in under-resourced communities or where state support is inconsistent.

Finally, *at the 'innovation' (meso) level, an important barrier stems from the design or logistics of the DI itself.* Poorly structured processes, unclear goals, or insufficiently prepared implementation teams can undermine the scalability potential (in any direction) of an innovation (Warren, 2025; Suiter & Reuchamps, 2017; Caluwaerts & Reuchamps, 2023). If a process is overly localized or lacks clear pathways for scaling, its impact may remain limited to a single place or issue (Purcell, 2006; Falanga, 2024). Some processes rely too heavily on either digital or in-person methods, excluding those who cannot access one or the other (Rucht, 2012). Others use biased recruitment strategies, such as only inviting politically active individuals or failing to ensure demographic diversity, which further limits inclusiveness and representativeness (Smith, 2009).

Table 5. Major Barriers to Scaling Democratic Innovations

Barrier Type	Description	Key References
<i>Regulatory / Institutional (Macro level)</i>	<i>Bureaucratic logics prioritizing risk-aversion, control, and efficiency; lack of administrative capacity.</i>	<i>Meier et al. (2019); Corbett (2018)</i>
<i>Socio-Political (Macro level)</i>	<i>Elite resistance, indifference, or selective support based on strategic interests or scepticism toward citizen competence.</i>	<i>Sønderskov (2020); Barry & Bannister (2014); Junis et al. (2020)</i>
<i>Cultural / Cognitive (Micro level)</i>	<i>Low civic knowledge, weak trust in the legitimacy or value of participation.</i>	<i>Gastil & Richards (2013); Christensen et al. (2016)</i>
<i>Resource-Based (Micro level)</i>	<i>Limited funding, staff, expertise, and support infrastructure; barriers to access in low-resource or politically marginal settings.</i>	<i>Barry & Bannister (2014); Janssen et al. (2012); Schradie (2018)</i>
<i>Design / Procedural / Logistical (Meso level)</i>	<i>Poor process design, vague agendas, biased recruitment, exclusive formats (digital-only or</i>	<i>Warren (2025); Reuchamps & Suiter (2016); Pogrebinschi & Ryan (2018); Purcell</i>

in-person-only), lack of scalability or institutional links. (2006); Rucht (2012); Smith (2011); Falanga (2024)

2.2 Overcoming Barriers

Recognizing the barriers to scaling democratic innovations is only part of the picture. Equally important is identifying the conditions under which these innovations are more likely to grow, deepen, or become embedded in governance. This section offers a first step toward that understanding.

This analytical framework does not aim to establish rigid causal rules, that is the role of a fuller Theory of Scaling to come following empirical investigation. Instead, drawing on a broad, structured review of the literature, we identify and organise key conditions that may help democratic innovations overcome barriers and generate meaningful change across the four different scaling dimensions presented above. Our goal here is to structure and prioritise these enabling conditions to sketch a range of plausible pathways through which scaling might occur, not to provide an exhaustive list.

We also group these conditions across three analytical levels: the broader institutional and political environment (macro), the features of the innovation itself (meso), and the actors who design, support, or implement it (micro). This helps make sense of how different factors interact to support scaling. In doing so, we address a critical gap in much of the existing literature on democratic innovations, which, despite recent comparative efforts, has often focused on standout cases. As Spada and Ryan (2017) note, this can overlook the range of contextual factors needed for democratic innovations' success and replication. By broadening the focus to these enabling conditions, we lay the groundwork for more realistic and adaptable strategies for scaling democratic innovations. The following sections describe each category and explore how they relate to the four scaling dimensions.

2.2.1. Regulatory/Institutional Frameworks (Macro)

The broader institutional environment, its structures, rules, and administrative capacities significantly shape the prospects for scaling democratic innovations. Formal frameworks can either open pathways for scaling by encouraging participation and experimentation, or constrain it through rigidity, bureaucratic inertia or lack of procedural support.

For Scaling Out, the openness of institutional settings to innovation, decentralization and cross-jurisdictional experimentation is especially important. When governance structures are less centralized, more flexible and supportive of localized adaptation, democratic innovations find more space to replicate across different settings (Meier et al., 2019; Feeney & DeHart-Davis, 2009; Osborne & Plastrik, 1997). Administrative stability and logistical capacity, such as the ability to support replication, manage data, or facilitate local adaptations, can also play a key role (Ferreira & Allegretti, 2019).

In Scaling Deep, institutional support takes a different form. Embedding civic education, especially education oriented toward deliberative democratic values within formal systems such as schools,

universities and civic programs can profoundly gradually strengthen the cultural and normative foundations that sustain democratic innovations over time. Institutions that systematically teach deliberation, active citizenship, and democratic reasoning help cultivate citizens who are ready to engage meaningfully (Boggs, 1991; Carcasson & Sprain, 2012; Hanson & Howe, 2011; Levinson, 2012).

For Scaling In, the focus is on procedural scaffolding: whether institutions provide frameworks that support, incentivize, and standardize high-quality citizen participation. This includes establishing evaluation criteria, transparency requirements, feedback mechanisms and standardized guidelines for participatory processes. Institutional frameworks that encourage clear standards of fairness, inclusivity, and deliberative integrity provide essential support for maintaining internal quality as democratic innovations grow (Pogrebinschi & Ryan, 2018).

Finally, **for Scaling High**, the successful integration of democratic innovations into formal decision-making depends on administrative stability and logistical capacity. Institutions must have the organizational infrastructure to ‘absorb’ participatory processes, manage outcomes and translate citizen inputs into actionable policy. Without administrative pathways and consistent commitment, scaling into formal law or policy is difficult to achieve (Pogrebinschi & Ross, 2019; Corbett, 2018).

2.2.2. Socio-Political and Cultural Contexts (Macro)

The socio-political and cultural environment strongly influences scaling as well. Civic traditions, public discourse norms, civil society dynamics and elite behaviour collectively form the informal ecosystem that can either foster or hinder scaling processes.

For Scaling Out, the presence of a deliberative civic culture, where public dialogue is valued and citizens expect participation, creates fertile ground for the expansion and replication of democratic innovations (Theuwis et al., 2025). Civil society plays a vital reinforcing role: advocacy coalitions, grassroots mobilization, and organized public pressure can push for the broader adoption of participatory practices (Pogrebinschi & Ryan, 2018). Elite behaviour also matters. Political or administrative elites may support democratic innovations out of ideological commitment, practical interest, or in response to electoral or societal pressures that demand greater public engagement (Barry & Bannister, 2014; Junius et al., 2020).

Scaling Deep similarly depends on the cultural and normative foundations of democracy. Societies with strong traditions of civic engagement and deliberative public discourse and norms provide the social soil in which democratic participation, including through innovative mechanisms, can take root and foster deeper value shifts (Gherghina and Geissel, 2017; see also Theuwis et al., 2025). In such contexts, individuals are more likely to internalize democratic norms and maintain emotional and behavioural commitments over time. To capture this mechanism, the ScaleDem framework conceptualises Scaling Deep through a Context–Mechanism–Impact–Outcome (C–M–I–O) logic. Context conditions — including institutional environments, governance structures, and broader political-cultural settings — shape both the demand for innovation and the likelihood that deep transformation can endure.

This analytical backbone is structured through four clusters of variables:

- **Context conditions** shape the environments in which democratic innovations unfold, including institutional settings, families or domains of democratic innovations, governance structures, and macro-political-cultural settings. They determine both the demand for innovation — democratic deficits and legitimacy crises — and the likelihood that deep change can emerge and endure.
- **Social mechanisms** (or 'change-makers') are recurrent social, social-psychological, and cultural dynamics that generate transformation. They operate through interaction (social–interactive), internal reflection and affect (psychological), and narratives and symbols (cultural–creative).¹
- **Impacts** capture perceived changes across cognitive, normative, emotional, symbolic, and behavioural dimensions, while
- **Outcomes** assess their durability, diffusion, and connection to broader scaling processes.

For **Scaling In**, experimental evidence suggests that maintaining high-quality participation may benefit from similar cultural conditions. Where traditions or norms of civil dialogue and public engagement are strong, participants are more likely to respect the deliberative process standards norms, tolerate disagreement, and engage constructively, even as processes grow in size or complexity (Strandberg et al., 2019). This can make it easier to uphold standards of inclusivity, fairness, and integrity also besides the deliberative sphere, contributing to process continuity and fostering a learning-oriented environment.

In the case of **Scaling High**, socio-political practices again prove decisive. Civil society organizations and advocacy networks can create bottom-up pressure for institutionalization, helping to secure

¹ The notion of “social mechanisms” draws on established literatures in political and social theory, psychology and social psychology. Within the ScaleDem framework, these mechanisms are refined as “triggers” that, under certain conditions, can activate individual-level ‘deep’ change. Among them, different clusters of ‘change makers’ can be distinguished (cf. Coleman 1990; cf. Hedström & Swedberg 1998; cf. Tilly 2001):

- “Emotional triggers” are conceived as primary drivers of attention and motivation that condition whether individuals become open (or close) to cognitive and normative change pathways, hence affective catalysts of engagement or disaffection (Nussbaum 2013).
- “Cognitive triggers” are interpreted as catalysts of exposure to dissonance, new frames and reflection that induce learning, where change occurs when existing belief systems are challenged, destabilised, and restructured (Festinger 1972; Fishkin 2009; Kahneman 2011).
- “Normative triggers” are catalysts of value change, where norms shape behaviour when they are perceived as legitimate and internalised, often through communicative interaction and justification (Habermas 1984) and norm compliance in collective action (Ostrom 2005).
- “Identity triggers” are framed as catalysts of civic self-redefinition and belonging, where political change becomes durable when it is embedded in identity and belonging, not just attitudes (Honneth 1996; Brubaker 2004);
- “Behavioural triggers” are catalysts of action, habit formation, and practice, including “social-interactive triggers” of relational reinforcement and diffusion, where democratic change is socially embedded in trust and networks of cooperation that provide feedback, validation and mutual adjustment, stabilising or transforming individual orientations (Putnam 2002).

formal uptake of participatory processes (Pogrebinschi & Ryan, 2018). At the same time, the positive exposure of elites to democratic innovations, through past participation or observation, can reduce scepticism and foster support (Sønderskov, 2020) and even result in internal champions. More broadly, elite receptivity may stem from electoral incentives, pre-existing ideological commitments, or responses to societal demands for greater transparency and inclusion (Junius et al., 2020).

2.2.3. Characteristics and Resources of Innovation Implementers (Micro)

Who leads a democratic innovation, and how, can have a significant impact on its ability to scale. The motivations, strategic orientation and practical capacities of initiators and implementers often determine whether an innovation remains a localized experiment or evolves into a systemically impactful process. As research in public innovation highlights (van Lunenburg et al., 2020), these actor-level enablers typically take three forms: **willingness** (strategic ambition), **ability** (skills and competencies), and **resource access** (organizational and material support).

For **Scaling Out**, the ambition to reach broader and more diverse publics must be matched with strong outreach and communication skills. Innovations are more likely to scale horizontally when implementers intentionally design for mass inclusion and know how to mobilize different publics across contexts (van Lunenburg et al., 2020). This outward scaling also hinges on access to funding and partnership networks that can help expand reach, particularly in contexts where public engagement depends on digital tools, community-based intermediaries, or targeted outreach (Newton, 2012; Schradie, 2018; Sønderskov, 2020).

Scaling Deep, by contrast, requires a different set of capacities. Implementers must be able to engage people not just intellectually, but emotionally, connecting with their values, identities, and lived experiences. This might involve historically grounded civic education (Nelsen, 2023), or storytelling approaches that resonate with participants' sense of meaning and belonging (Molder et al., 2024).

For **Scaling In**, the focus is on process quality, making sure that internal process standards remain high even as participation expands. This demands skilled facilitation and design leadership, particularly in moderating discussions, crafting structured formats, and resolving conflict. In this context, resource needs are not just financial, they also involve time, space, and professional support to ensure that the process is thoughtful and inclusive (Newton, 2012).

Finally, **Scaling High** depends heavily on navigating institutions and building alliances. Implementers need to understand policy environments, form cross-sector partnerships, and frame innovation outcomes in ways that resonate with decision-makers. Often, scaling to this level requires leveraging institutional channels—through formal invitations, insider networks, or coalitions with supportive actors inside government. In Brazil, for example, bureaucratic activists within the state have played a key role in advancing and institutionalising participatory initiatives, showing how committed officials can drive democratic innovations into formal structures (Abers, 2019).

2.2.4. Characteristics of the Innovation Itself (Meso)

The way a democratic innovation is structured and implemented can affect how easily it scales. Some innovations are designed with flexibility, adaptability or deliberative strength, qualities that make them more likely to work in new settings or reach more people. Others, by contrast, may be more context-dependent or limited by rigid formats. These intrinsic characteristics influence how well an innovation can stretch across space, deepen its cultural reach, or anchor itself in formal institutions (Geissel, 2012; Escobar & Elstub, 2017).

For **Scaling Out**, designs that enable both the inclusion of more and more diverse participants and the replication of processes across contexts are particularly important. Inclusive models, such as hybrid formats, random or disproportionate selection (especially when stakes are unevenly distributed), can expand participation beyond the already engaged (Rucht, 2012; Meylan-Stevenson et al., 2024; Newton, 2012). Replicability also benefits from structured and standardized formats (e.g., clear agendas, expert Q&A, group deliberation, consensus reporting, campaign toolkit, process guidebook, etc) that can be reproduced “as is” or adapted with minimal redesign, especially when supported by toolkits or facilitation guides (Suiter & Reuchamps, 2017).

For **Scaling Deep**, design features that foster emotional resonance and long-term engagement are key. Repeated formats that allow participants to re-engage over time (Fernández-Martínez et al., 2020), or designs that bring in lived experiences, such as personal testimonies or parallel group formats, can help bridge technical content with day-to-day realities, supporting value internalization and a sense of civic identity.

For **Scaling In**, high-quality processes depend on more fine-grained procedural scaffolding: clear speaking rules, multi-phase structures, and carefully designed agendas (Suiter & Reuchamps, 2017; Mikhaylovskaya, 2023). Selection procedures again matter, random or disproportionate selection strategies can help ensure legitimacy, while designs that incorporate personal narrative alongside expert input maintain both inclusion and relevance. Strategic issue framing, particularly avoiding highly polarized topics, can also contribute to maintaining process integrity (Rucht, 2012).

Beyond design features, the capacity to improve internally over time is shaped by structural conditions that vary across DI families. In deliberative and digital innovations, practitioners typically retain considerable discretion to adjust recruitment strategies, facilitation methods, information provision, and — in digital settings — technological or algorithmic parameters between cycles (Geissel, 2012; Caluwaerts & Reuchamps, 2023; Jacquet et al., 2023). By contrast, in administrative, direct democratic, and especially electoral innovations, redesign is often constrained by procurement rules, statutory requirements, or constitutional entrenchment, and may require legislative or regulatory reform (Norris, 2014, 2015). In such cases, learning processes tend to operate through oversight bodies, audit mechanisms, or formal review procedures rather than practitioner-driven iteration. In digital and AI-mediated settings, rapid iteration creates both opportunities and risks: without structured evaluation and independent audit, algorithmic systems may reproduce or amplify biases at scale (McKinney, 2024; McKinney & Chwalisz, 2025).

These differences are structural rather than incidental: they reflect variation in design discretion, regulatory constraints, and the institutional distance between those who administer an innovation and those who hold authority to reform it. While they do not redefine what Scaling In entails, they significantly affect the speed, scope, and political feasibility of internal improvement. Lastly, for **Scaling High**, strategic alignment between the design of the innovation and the of policymaking institutions increases the chances of formal uptake. Innovations that frame their work in ways that resonate with administrative logic or legal structures, are more likely to be institutionalized (Newton, 2012; Rucht, 2012). At the same time, if they succeed to frame a contentious topic well and create solutions/agreements, this might also support institutionalization.

Table 6. Key Enabling Factors Across Scaling Dimensions

Enabling Factor	Scaling Out	Scaling Deep	Scaling In	Scaling High
Innovation Characteristics (Meso)	✓	✓	✓	
Modular and replicable design formats	✓		✓	
Embeddedness of lived experience/testimony		✓	✓	
Structured deliberative agendas and phases	✓		✓	
Strategic framing and alignment with less polarized issues			✓	✓
Motivations and Abilities of Implementers (Micro)	✓	✓	✓	✓
Outreach and communication skills	✓			
Storytelling, civic education skills		✓		
Facilitation and deliberative design skills			✓	
Advocacy, institutional navigation, coalition-building				✓
Resource Access (Macro)	✓	✓	✓	✓
Funding and networks for expansion	✓			
Partnerships with education, media, civic orgs		✓		
Resources for process quality (time, staff, training)			✓	
Access to policymakers and formal institutional channels				✓
Regulatory / Institutional Frameworks (Macro)	✓	✓	✓	✓
Open frameworks	✓			
Civic education integration into institutions		✓		
Procedural standards for participatory processes			✓	
Administrative/logistical stability and capacity				✓

Socio-Political and Cultural Context (Macro)	✓	✓	✓	✓
Deliberative civic culture and public discourse	✓	✓	✓	
Civil society pressure and mobilization	✓			✓
Elites' positive exposure, electoral pressure, ideological commitment	✓			✓

3. Relationship Between Scaling Dimensions and Feedback Loops

Scaling dimensions are not isolated from one another. In practice, we assume that progress along one dimension can open up possibilities for progress in others. Scaling often unfolds through feedback loops between dimensions, where developments in one area create favourable conditions for scaling elsewhere. Analytically and empirically, these potential interactions can be explored by examining how scaling indicators shift over time, either in single cases or ecosystems of innovations. Theoretical expectations about these pathways can later inform causal hypotheses, but at this stage, it is useful to map plausible connections. The example provided below offers a preliminary illustration of these feedback loops.

Scaling High can act as a catalyst for other forms of scaling. Legal mandates and formal recognition may increase the visibility, sustainability, and replicability of innovations, thereby supporting Scaling Out. For instance, if participatory budgeting becomes legally required across municipalities, it naturally expands participation across wider territories and demographics. Moreover, institutionalization may also foster Scaling In, by increasing the motivation of actors engaged in democratic practices, and by securing stable funding, professional facilitation, and clearer procedural standards that improve deliberative quality. Finally, formal uptake has the potential to enhance Scaling Deep, as citizens may develop greater trust in democratic processes when they see that participation can influence real-world outcomes.

Scaling Deep can also strengthen other dimensions. A strong civic culture based on deliberative principles may support Scaling In, by encouraging respectful engagement, tolerance, and thoughtful deliberation among participants. In parallel, widespread cultural support for participation may reduce institutional resistance, facilitating Scaling High when reforms are proposed or when democratic innovations seek formal adoption.

Scaling Out, by broadening participation, may generate feedback into both deliberative quality and democratic culture. Greater diversity of participants, if well-managed, can enrich discussions and support Scaling In by enhancing the inclusiveness and nuance of deliberations. Expanding participation can also contribute to Scaling Deep, particularly when groups historically excluded from public decision-making gain a sense of empowerment and belonging through meaningful engagement. It could perhaps also come with threats for that particular dimension, if it dilutes potential for consensus due to greater group interests and fewer points of agreement. Additionally, under certain conditions, broad participation may create political momentum that supports Scaling High, although volume alone is rarely sufficient without strategic advocacy and elite responsiveness.

For **Scaling In**, high-quality participatory processes can contribute to the development of deeper democratic dispositions among individuals exposed to the innovation (Scaling Deep). When participation is experienced as fair and meaningful, individuals may come to engage more strongly with democratic practices, develop a clearer sense of civic identity, and feel a greater sense of political

efficacy. At the same time, cultural norms that emphasize equality, mutual respect, transparency, shared responsibility and compromise can help sustain process quality over time.

Table 7. Possible Feedback Loops Between Scaling Dimensions

<i>Scaling High ↔ Scaling Out</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Institutional integration can facilitate broader outreach and replication.</i> • <i>Widespread participation can, under certain conditions, generate momentum for formal institutional uptake.</i>
<i>Scaling High ↔ Scaling In</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Formalization and stable support can enhance process quality and deliberative standards.</i> • <i>High-quality processes can build legitimacy and support, making institutionalization more feasible.</i>
<i>Scaling High ↔ Scaling Deep</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Institutional recognition can reinforce trust in democracy and deepen civic norms.</i> • <i>A democratic culture supportive of participation can lower barriers to formal embedding.</i>
<i>Scaling Out ↔ Scaling In</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Expanding participation can diversify and enrich deliberative quality if well-designed.</i> • <i>Strong internal process quality can sustain expansion by maintaining legitimacy and engagement.</i>
<i>Scaling Out ↔ Scaling Deep</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Broad participation, especially by marginalized groups, can foster empowerment and civic identity transformation.</i> • <i>A culture of engagement and empowerment can, in turn, support sustained and expanded participation.</i>
<i>Scaling In ↔ Scaling Deep</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>High-quality processes can cultivate deeper democratic values among participants.</i> • <i>Strong civic norms and emotional ties to democracy can sustain high quality standards over time.</i>

Overall, scaling should be understood as a dynamic, interconnected process, where multiple dimensions may reinforce or unlock one another over time. Recognizing these possible feedback loops is key to building a flexible and realistic understanding of how democratic innovations grow and endure. This is not to say that there may not also be negative feedback loops between scaling dimensions, a hypothesis we want to further explore in a second stage of the process. For instance, Scaling deep might be impeded by the formal nature of certain process (Scaling High) which can impede a certain sense of freedom and creativity. Similarly, accelerated Scaling Out and replication might happen at the cost of Scaling in and the quality of the process. Such negative correlations or even causations are equally worth exploring.

This raises new questions in turn that we hope to address in the second stage: what is the dominant direction of causality between these dimensions? Do we observe general patterns of sequencing between them? Under which conditions are they mutually reinforcing? How do we know that scaling dimensions affect each other, rather than due to some common external cause? What do these interactions look like in the eyes of individuals or groups engaged in democratic innovations?

Since each democratic innovation occurs within a specific institutional, social, and temporal context, we find that some contexts are more amenable to certain scaling dimensions rather than others. For instance, some contexts exhibiting strong state-society relations may lead to strong policy integration (Scaling High) while struggling to engage broadly (Scaling Out). Other contexts with high social capital may foster deep civic engagement (Scaling Deep) without formal recognition. Each innovation thus reflects a **distinct scaling profile**, a unique combination of progress along these dimensions, shaped by its goals, design, and environment.

Figure 1: Scaling Dimensions as Spider Charts – Example Representation

To capture this diversity, we propose representing the scaling profile of a democratic innovation using a **spider chart**. This visual tool allows us to map the relative strength or extent of scaling across the four dimensions, offering a clear, comparative snapshot of how an innovation is evolving at a given moment. An example graphic is provided above.

Spider charts lend themselves to different degrees of achievement along each of the dimensions that can take on values between 0 and 1. Moreover, spider charts allow to ‘measure’ in an intuitive way not only the overall scaling potential of a given innovation but also the theoretical potential of a combination of innovations. In keeping with the spatial metaphors attached to each of our four dimensions, a spider diagram attached to a given case or case type offers an immediate and intuitive measure of the “democratic space” opened up by the said case.

The configurational nature of scaling dynamics outlined above suggests that no single dimension is likely to act as a universal driver. Instead, scaling trajectories emerge from combinations of institutional embedding, cultural depth, participatory expansion, and internal process quality, embedded in specific contextual environments. This logic of interaction, sequencing, and potential trade-offs calls for a comparative method capable of identifying recurring configurations rather than isolated variables. For this reason, the project mobilises Qualitative Comparative Analysis (QCA) as a core comparative anchor. QCA allows us to identify recurring scaling profiles and combinations of conditions across cases, while dimension-specific methodologies provide the detailed empirical insight necessary to unpack individual dimensions and trace the causal processes through which scaling unfolds. Together, these approaches enable both comparative generalisation and mechanism-sensitive explanation

This in turn can point to one of the value-added of the ScaleDem project as a whole. This analytical framework has started hinting towards plausible pathways through which scaling might occur, on the basis of which a first iteration of a Qualitative Comparative Analysis of the different cases identified in the [ScaleDem Knowledge Map](#) has been implemented. On such a ground, an initial Theory of Change will be able to offer hypotheses about “scaling combinatrix” to be further tested and refined throughout the entire project duration, in subsequent Work Packages, and notably through ScaleDem Scaling Grounds.

4. Research Design: Grounding the Analytical Architecture in Empirical Knowledge

Building on the conceptual and operational structure presented in the previous sections, this section outlines how the ScaleDem framework is translated into a systematic empirical strategy. The research design combines qualitative and quantitative methods to collect and analyze data on cases of democratic innovation.

This section first describes the methodological strategy's phases for WP1 (Knowledge-based Theory of Scaling). Second, it explains the data-collection strategy and its expected product, a Knowledge Map of Democratic Innovations. Third, it outlines the use of qualitative comparative analysis (QCA) to examine the relationships among different dimensions of scaling. Fourth, it outlines the strategy for rolling out the SenseMaker methodology to expand the dataset and support the interpretive analysis of results. Fifth, it summarizes the strategies for in-depth analysis of each dimension. Finally, it explains how iterative interpretive analysis will produce a Knowledge-based Theory of Scaling.

4.1 Methodological Strategy

To build a grounded theory of scaling, we adopt an exploratory sequential research design structured into five temporal stages and eight analytical phases (see Figure 2). These stages align with the key outputs of this Work Package beyond the Analytical Framework. The first stage produced the initial iteration of the Knowledge Map (M6, May 2025). The second stage developed a Qualitative Comparative Analysis (QCA) model and translated its findings into preliminary, actionable recommendations for practitioners, policymakers, and the project's Scaling Grounds work packages (M10, September 2025). The third stage expands the empirical base through interviews, focus groups, an online survey and a Delphi process, alongside a second iteration of the Knowledge Map (M16, April 2026). The fourth stage focuses on the systematic analysis of this extended dataset. Finally, the fifth stage updates the QCA model developed earlier and integrates all findings into a Knowledge-Based Theory of Scaling (M24, November 2026).

Figure 2: Procedural Diagram for a Theory of Scaling Democratic Innovations

4.2 The Knowledge Map as Structured Case Universe

The empirical foundation of the project is the ScaleDem Knowledge Map of Democratic Innovations. As introduced earlier, the Knowledge Map (KM) compiles democratic innovation (DI) cases across families, governance levels, policy domains, and geographical contexts. It functions not merely as a repository but as a structured case universe designed to support comparative testing. Balancing principles guide the inclusion and expansion of cases across: DI families (deliberative, participatory, administrative, digital, direct, and electoral); governance levels (local to supranational); regional variation within Europe; temporal trajectories; and institutional settings.

In its first iteration, the KM includes 70 cases selected according to the mentioned criteria from the Cordis database using search strings. In the second iteration, the sample is expanded to 300 cases, of which 200 are selected from Cordis and 100 from the Participedia database to account for non-EU-funded projects in Europe. The KM is a living project throughout the duration of the project and will include further cases beyond the second iteration, drawn from the Resonance Space (T2.3.1) and Reversing the Gaze (T5.3) tasks, beyond the scope of Europe and the work of WP1.

This progressive expansion ensures that scaling dynamics are examined across a sufficiently diverse and balanced empirical landscape.

4.3 QCA as Comparative Backbone

The interactions between scaling dimensions described in Section 3 imply that no single dimension is solely responsible for scaling outcomes. Instead, distinct scaling trajectories emerge from combinations of institutional embedding (Scaling High), participatory expansion (Scaling Out), civic-cultural transformation (Scaling Deep), and internal process quality (Scaling In), embedded in specific contextual environments.

We hypothesize that different combinations of scaling dimensions yield divergent scaling outcomes. We set out to tackle this by using Qualitative Comparative Analysis (QCA), which constitutes the comparative backbone of the project. QCA enables us to: 1) identify recurring configurations (pathways) of scaling dimensions across cases, 2) capture pathways leading to similar scaling impact, and 3) test how contextual factors interact with scaling dimensions.

Qualitative Comparative Analysis (QCA) operationalises explanatory conditions—here, the four scaling dimensions—into calibrated measures applied systematically across all cases. Each democratic innovation (DI) is thus represented as a specific configuration of conditions, allowing cases to be compared in terms of the pathways they follow. By examining these configurations, QCA identifies which combinations of conditions are associated with particular scaling outcomes. In this way, it provides the comparative backbone of the project: revealing recurring patterns across cases and grounding the feedback-loop logic in empirically observed configurations rather than isolated factors.

In the first iteration of the QCA, we analysed 70 cases drawn from the initial version of the Knowledge Map. This involved constructing a model based on 16 questions to operationalise the four scaling dimensions, alongside three questions capturing scaling outcomes, as detailed in [D1.2](#). In the next phase, this model will be refined and applied to the expanded dataset of more than 200 cases included in the second version of the Knowledge Map, with additional data collected through the SenseMaker survey.

4.4 SenseMaker as Interpretive Data Collection

As the first iteration of the QCA relied primarily on document-based data, we sought to strengthen the analysis by expanding and deepening the empirical base for the second iteration. To this end, we employ the SenseMaker survey, a method developed within the Cynefin Company framework to capture the meaning of social processes through participants' own interpretations, going beyond purely descriptive or "objective" data. We selected this approach over conventional interviews in order to reach a large and diverse group of organisers and participants across approximately 200 DI cases.

SenseMaker engages respondents by first inviting them to share a short narrative about their experience with a given DI case, followed by a set of open and structured questions that prompt them to interpret key aspects of that experience—its context, underlying mechanisms, perceived impacts, activation dynamics, and scaling outcomes. These questions are aligned with the operational logic of the QCA model.

The collected data are then processed within the same system, generating both case-specific and cross-case insights. This adds an initial analytical layer directly to the data collection process, which in turn feeds into the broader interpretive analysis, complemented by qualitative methods such as interviews, focus groups, and the Delphi process.

4.5 Dimension-Specific Methodologies and Mechanism-Sensitive Depth

While QCA enables cross-case configurational comparison, the dimension-specific methodologies described earlier provide detailed empirical insight into how individual dimensions unfold and how causal processes operate within cases.

Each scaling dimension is associated with specific sub-dimensions and indicator families, operationalised through distinct methodological strategies:

- **Scaling Out** employs mapping, qualitative content analysis, and process tracing to detect horizontal, vertical, and transversal expansion, and to identify diffusion mechanisms and contextual enablers or obstacles.
- **Scaling High** draws on interviews and focus groups with policymakers and administrators to investigate political buy-in, legal integration, administrative integration, and institutional blockages.
- **Scaling In** is explored through a two-round group Delphi process that refines reflections on the tradeoffs relevant to the aspects of inclusiveness, integrity, effectiveness, continuity, and learning.
- **Scaling Deep** is empirically explored through the SenseMaker's narrative inquiry framework, capturing multidimensional change and tracing its emergence through social mechanisms.

These methodological streams generate the empirical insights through which sub-dimensions and indicator families are assessed. They support process tracing and the identification of underlying

mechanisms, thereby unpacking the context-dependent variation of scaling pathways that configurational QCA alone cannot fully capture.

Within this architecture, QCA and dimension-specific analyses are complementary: QCA identifies recurring scaling profiles and cross-case configurations, while dimension-specific approaches provide in-depth evidence on how individual dimensions operate and on the mechanisms that drive them.

4.6 Operationalisation and Validation

The operationalisation of scaling builds directly on the sub-dimensions and indicator families presented in earlier sections. For each scaling dimension (Out, High, Deep, In), sub-dimensions and associated indicator families provide the analytical structure through which cases are examined. The illustrative indicators specified in the tables above serve as empirical entry points for assessing the presence, intensity, or absence of scaling features across cases.

Rather than assuming a fixed metric at this stage, the project adopts a light calibration approach. Cases are assessed along each dimension using clearly defined qualitative anchors (e.g., low, medium, high presence of scaling features), grounded in the empirical material generated through the dimension-specific methodologies. This approach enables structured and consistent comparison across cases while retaining sensitivity to contextual variation.

These calibrated assessments generate a four-dimensional scaling profile for each case. Such profiles can be visualised descriptively (for instance through the spider charts presented in Section 3) and serve as structured inputs for comparative configurational analysis (QCA). The purpose is not to reduce complex processes to rigid numerical scores, but to ensure transparent and replicable comparative positioning of cases within the broader analytical framework.

To enhance reliability, Internal calibration discussions across teams will align interpretations of sub-dimensions and qualitative anchors through joint review of pilot cases and documented adjustment of scoring criteria. In addition, external feedback from practitioners and advisory actors will be sought to ensure conceptual clarity and usability. The operational framework remains iterative and may be refined as empirical work progresses and additional cases are incorporated into the Knowledge Map.

4.7 Iterative Refinement, Integration, and a Theory of Change

The research design is explicitly iterative. Initial configurational findings and mechanism-sensitive analyses will inform the development of a first Theory of Change (D1.3), articulating plausible scaling pathways and combinatorial patterns. These hypotheses will be refined over time as new cases are incorporated into the Knowledge Map and as dimension-specific analyses deepen.

Through this integrated design - structured case universe, configurational comparison, sub-dimension operationalisation, and mechanism-sensitive inquiry - the ScaleDem project advances a comprehensive and empirically grounded understanding of how democratic innovations scale across contexts and dimensions.

Conclusion

This framework provides a structured, multidimensional lens to understand how democratic innovations can scale. It identifies a broad set of enabling conditions which, depending on their specific configuration, may help innovations overcome barriers and achieve progress across different scaling dimensions. Some factors may be particularly decisive in certain contexts; others may compensate for what is missing elsewhere. The relevance of any one condition is likely to depend on the scaling goal, institutional setting, and design of the innovation itself.

Importantly, at this stage of the project, the present framework does not propose a universal formula for success, nor does it claim to establish conditions of causal necessity or sufficiency. Rather, it maps a **range of plausible pathways** through which scaling might occur. It serves as an analytical scaffold, helping practitioners and researchers identify key dimensions, analytical standpoints, and corresponding factors at play, and assess where support, adaptation, or intervention might be needed, and by whom.

The next step is theoretically ambitious yet empirically grounded. Building on the methodological formula outlined in the document — combining an iterative QCA strategy with complementary mixed methods tailored to each scaling dimension — we will refine and substantiate our Theory of Change. This approach will allow us to systematically examine how enabling conditions combine and interact, and to identify the causal mechanisms that explain how and why scaling unfolds differently across contexts.

Our objective is to open the “black box” of scaling dynamics: to clarify how distinct trajectories emerge, when particular factors become necessary or sufficient, and under what conditions they may substitute for one another or instead reinforce each other. By analysing configurational patterns across cases and dimensions, we aim not only to confirm expected dynamics, but also to uncover counterintuitive insights — identifying seemingly small conditions that trigger substantial effects, or, conversely, widely held assumptions that may not withstand empirical scrutiny

In this sense, the analytical framework presented here is not a final answer, but a foundation: a way to better observe, compare, and understand the complex realities of scaling democratic innovations.

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